

Social

LORD KRISHNA IN ILAYARAJA'S 'NATHA VELIYINILE'- A CRITICAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This article, Lord Krishna in Ilayaraja's Nathaveliyinile' tries to prove the power of 'Gurus' (Residential Teachers) on helpless disciples. Even Lord Krishna violates the ethics of war to fulfill the ambition of Karma; He succeeds too. As musician Ilayaraja is an atheist and follower of Hinduism, he tries to reveal the cunningness played by God over man in an add hour. He strongly refuses the approach of Lord Krishna on Arjuna's innocence. Thus he says no need of showing 'Vishvarooba Dharsan' in battle field (Gurusetra). The researcher supports the view of the poet.

Keywords:

Karma : The unknown birth duty of a soul decided by fate.

The Gita : Srimad Bagavad Gita. (Part of 'Maha Bharatham)

Pandavas : Five sons of King Pandu.

Gowravas : Hundred sons of King Yudistran

Gurusatra : Battle field of Pandavas and Gowravas.

Visva Roopam : The real, Huge image of anyone; Specially of God.

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1. INTRODUCTION

UNIQUENESS OF BHARATHAM (INDIA)

'Bharatham 'alias India is a Holy land in the entire Universe. One has to do million years of 'Thabas'(A kind of hard prayer years together without food, water etc. to convince a God to fulfill a wish) to be a son/ daughter of this soil. Any land may have wealth, power etc. but India is a land full of Peace, Holy customs, Living ethics etc. If anyone needs or wants to know the eternal path; then it is inevitable to follow the Holy path of Indian religious nuances, which is an evidence and encouragement to attain peace of mind and blissful eternity.

Let us move further to classify the richness of this Holy Land. India is the only land which has rich traditions of ‘Vedas, Puranas and highly ritual epics etc. Among them ‘Ramayana’ and ‘Maha Bharatha’ are even today sung, heard, recited, studied, taught etc.

SUPREMACY OF ‘THE GITA’

‘Maha Bharatha’ (The Gita) is supposed to be the supreme source of all the four Vedas. (Rick, Yajur, Sama and Othervana). It is emanated directly from the Holy Lips of Lord Krishna. India and its Hindu culture cannot be isolated from these Vedas and Maharisi Vyasa is the compiler of ‘The Gita’.

The Gita is superior even to the Ganga (River Ganga). Hindus believe that those who take a plunge in the water of the Ganga can liberate themselves from the chain of Birth and worldly sufferings. But those who take a dive in the Gita, not alone liberate themselves but acquire the ability to liberate others too; because the Ganga springs from the Holy feet of the Lord but the Gita has emanated from the Holy lips of Lord.

The Gita is uttered by Lord Krishna to Arjuna in the battle field of ‘Gurusetra’ (Where Maha Bharatha war was conducted between ‘Pandavas’ and ‘Gowravas’ for eighteen days). When Arjuna felt depressed and expressed his inability to fight against his kith and kin, relatives and Gurus; Lord Krishna convinced him that nothing is done by him because everything has already been planned. Arjuna is killing the souls which had already been killed; in other words nothing is done by him, everything is done by Him. When Arjuna refused to obey the words of Lord Krishna, He showed his ‘Visvarootha Dharsan’ means Krishna’s real image as God and His omnipresence. Then Arjuna realized everything and obeyed the orders of Lord Krishna.

EXCLUSIVE IDENTITY OF TAMIL CULTURE

Even in India, Tamilnadu has had exclusive, peculiar, precious, excelling powers and approach to Life; here life does not mean simply survival but to find out the core and taste the essence of Life. Ancient Tamil Saints, sages and fore fathers paved a clear way to lead the life on earth.

Saint, Thirumoolar in his book ‘Thirumandiram’ says, “Ondre Kulam, Oruvane Devan”. (Entire soul in the world is one; likewise the eternal power is one). Branches of a tree may differ, but root and trunk are one. People have only two types of lives; one is internal (personal), other is external (social).

Spoken language is divided into three categories; Iyal, Isai, Nadaham’ means spoken, musical and dramatic. Aim of life is divided into four categories; ‘Aram’ (Sharing or yielding to the downtrodden), ‘Porul’(In order to yield one must earn in the right path), ‘Inbam’ (When you share your excess to others, automatically pleasure would engulf you), ‘Veedu’ (Live happy and let others also be happy, you may attain so called Heaven or eternity).

Living land was divided into five categories; ‘Kurinji (Mountain and its surroundings),’ Mullai’ (Forest and its surroundings), ‘Marutham’ (Green fields and its surroundings), ‘Neithal’ (Sea and its surroundings), ‘Paalai’ (Desert and its surroundings).

Taste was divided into six; Musical note was divided into seven; Direction has been divided into eight; expression of a person is divided into nine types, 'Navarasa' etc.

Tamilnadu is the holy land of Temples; Eighteen 'Siddas'(Powerful saints who mastered everything in the world and lived more than thousands of years and are worshipped equal to God even today). Arts were divided into sixty four categories. Tamil civilization has rich and varied heritage. The aim of living according to Tamil culture is to attain everlasting Bliss through cultural richness.

Recent scientific inventions have proved that 'Tamil' is the first and for most language in the world. In this language, musician, 'Ilayaraja' has written a book entitled, 'Natha Veliyinile'(Natham-Music; Veliyinile-entire atmosphere).

MUSICIAN ILAYARAJA – A BRIEF INTRODUCTION

Ilayaraja, a leading inevitable musician of Tamil film industry, ruled the Tamil film songs from 1970s to 1990s. He is the only Tamil musician who has written notes to Symphony music.

Ilayaraja was born in a small village, Pannaipuram near Madurai, Tamilnadu. He has had interest in music from his boyhood itself. His musical interest was encouraged by his brother, 'Pavalar Varatharajan'. In 1968, he came to Chennai (then Madras) and after many hardships he became a notable musician and in the middle of 1980s, he became an inevitable musician and still continues his musical journey.

Apart from his music, he has written few books in Tamil. The researcher has taken one of his books, 'Natha Veliyinile' for his research article. This is a book full of verses, articles and little biographical notes too. The researcher would like to analyze a particular poem; 'Anniyamaa?' means does not a part of it? ; Otherwise both are same. As Ilayaraja is a deep follower of Hinduism, he has written the poem about Arjuna and Lord Krishna. (Natha Veliyinile, page No. 118).

POEM 'ANNIYAMAA?' AND QUOTES FROM 'THE GITA'

The poet asks, "When Arjuna refused to fight against his dear and near ones, Lord Krishna would have induced Arjuna's sub conscious mind to fight instead of showing His 'Vishvarootha Dharsan'; because according to Hinduism every 'Jeevathma' (Individual soul) consists 'Paramaathmaa' (footage of Almighty). Then why Lord Krishna showed His original Appearance to Arjuna. Does not it mean, "I am the Almighty, I am the Boss here. Obey my orders Arjuna. Otherwise you have to face the consequences"?"

The poet does slightly mean that Lord Krishna did not stimulate Arjuna for fighting, instead he was gently threatened to obey the orders of the Lord. It may be for good reasons, but the ethics of war seems to be controversial. (From 'Natha Veliyinile', Page No.118 : Title : Anniyama?)
Source Language : Tamil.

Transliteration

Arjunan yaar enpathai
Krisnan katti irukka vendum
Atahi vittu vittu
Ennai yaarenru Ninaitthai
Itho par en sua roopathai
(Translation by the researcher)

Translation

who is Arjuna?
Krishna would have shown it.
Instead of that/ apart from that
what do you think of myself?
See, this is my real appearance.---

From the Gita:

*Drstvemam svajanam krsna yuyutsum samupasthitam
Sidanti mama gatrani mukham ca parisusyati
Vepathusca sarire me romaharsasca jayate.*

Arjuna said: Krsna, at the sight of these kinsmen arrayed for battle, my limbs gives way, and my mouth is parching; nay, a shiver runs through my body and hair stands upright. (Srimad Bhagavadgita, Chapter –I, Slogan : second half of 28 and 29)

*Gandivam sransate hastattvakcaiva paridahyate
Na ca saknomyavasthatum bhramativa ca me manah*

The bow, Gandiva, slips from my hand and my skin too burns all over; my brain is whirling, as it were, and I can stand no longer. (Chapter-I; Slogan:30)

*Kutastva kasmalamidam visame samupasthitam
Anaryajustamasvargyamkirtikaramarjuna*

Sri Bhagavan said : Arjuna, how has this infatuation overtaken you at this odd hour? It is shunned by noble souls; neither will it bring heaven, nor fame, to you. (Chapter-2; slogan:2)

*Adrstapurvam hrsito'smi drstva bhayena ca pravyathitam mano me
tadeva me darsaya devarupam prasida deveva jagannivasa*

Having seen Your wondrous form, which was never seen before, I feel transported with joy; at the same time my mind is tormented by fear. Pray reveal to me that divine form, the form of Visnu with four arms; O Lord of celestials, Abode of the universe, be gracious. (Chapter-11; slogan: 45)

*Maya prasannena tavarjunedam rupam param darsitamatmayogat
tejomayam visvamanantamadyam yanme tvadanyena na drstapurvam*

Sri Bhagavan said : Arjuna! pleased with You, I have shown you, through My own power of Yoga, this supreme, effulgent, primal and infinite Cosmic Body, which was never seen before by anyone else than you. (Chapter-11; slogan-47)

*Yasya nahankrto bhavo buddhiryasya na lipyate
Hatvapi sa imallokanna hanta na nibadhyate.*

Sri Bhagavan said : He whose mind is free from the sense of doership, and whose reason is not tainted by worldly objects and activities, does not really slay, even having slaughtered all these creatures, nor is bound by sin. (Chapter-18; slogan-17)

*Nasto mohah smrtirlabdha tvatprasadanmayacyuta
Sthito'smi gatasandehah karisye vacanam tava.*

Arjuna said: Krsna, by your grace my delusion has fled and wisdom has been gained by me. I stand shorn of all doubts. I will do your bidding. (Chapter-18; slogan-73).

RESEARCHER'S VIEW

Here, researcher would like to add an apt point. A King Cobra unexpectedly meets an earth worm. King cobra orders the earthworm to do something which has not been carried out. Immediately the agitated cobra shows its real image to the earth worm and insists to obey. Is it fair on the part of the King cobra? Actually earth worm does not know what a snake is. Unable to understand and digest, out of magical swooning, it has to obey the orders of king cobra. It is a kind of threatening art or black magic.

2. CONCLUSION

Hence the researcher whole heartedly agrees and approves the fact of the poet. It must have been the duty of Lord Krishna to create self-realization within Arjuna rather than showing His 'Vishvaroop' to Arjuna. It shows the violation of war ethics and proves power mania.

3. REFERENCES

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